

Extractive Photometric Determination of Vanadium(V) with *N-m*-Chlorophenyl-2-Theno-Hydroxamic Acid in Presence of Thiocyanate

(Km.) K. PAUL and V. K. GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 010 (M. P.)

Manuscript received 22 May 1980, revised 8 January 1981, accepted 10 March 1981

Vanadium(V) reacts with *N-m*-chlorophenyl-2-theno-hydroxamic acid to form 1 : 2 (metal to ligand) complex containing a basic V=O group and an acidic -V-OH group which forms addition compound with thiocyanate to give a hyper or bathochromic effect in chloroform. On the basis of this bathochromic effect of thiocyanate with the reagent a highly selective and sensitive method for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) has been developed. The blue coloured complex of vanadium(V) is extractable in chloroform having the λ_{\max} 580 nm and ϵ_{\max} 7000 ± 50 l. mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The method has been applied for determination of traces of vanadium in steels. Mo(VI), W(VI) and Zr(IV) do not interfere.

VANADIUM(V) forms 1 : 2 complex with mono-basic and bidentate extracting agents containing donor oxygen groups. These complexes contain a basic V=O group as well as an acidic V-OH group in the same complex¹⁻³. V=O group of these complexes reacts with acidic substances to give a hyper and bathochromic effect in organic solvents⁴⁻⁶.

N-m-chlorophenyl-2-theno-hydroxamic acid I (*N-m*-CPTHA) is a typical monobasic and bidentate extracting agent which forms 1 : 2 complex with vanadium(V). The basic V=O group of this complex reacts with thiocyanate to give a hyper and bathochromic effect in chloroform.

The present paper describes the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of trace amount of vanadium(V) in presence of thiocyanate. The method is highly sensitive and selective having λ_{\max} 580 nm and ϵ_{\max} 7000 ± 50 l. mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Sandell's sensitivity is 0.00728 μ g V cm⁻².

The use of thiocyanate has already been reported in spectrophotometric determination of Ti and Nb⁹.

Mo(VI) W(VI) and Zr(IV) which interfere in the determination of vanadium with other *N*-aryl-hydroxamic acids do not interfere with *N-m*-CPTHA in presence of thiocyanate.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents : Carl Zeiss recording UV VIS spectrophotometer model GS-865 with 10 mm matched silica cells were used for the absorbance measurement.

Stock solution of vanadium was prepared by dissolving analytical grade ammonium metavanadate in glass distilled water. The vanadium content was determined by Hillebrand's method¹⁰, i.e., the vanadium is reduced by passing sulphur dioxide through the dilute sulphuric acid solution and boiling off the excess, then reduced solution is titrated with 0.1 *N* permanganate solution using Ferroin as indicator.

N-m-chlorophenyl-2-theno-hydroxamic acid was prepared by the condensation of 2 thienyl chloride and *m*-chlorophenyl-hydroxylamine by reported method¹¹ (m.p. -116°).

0.1% solution of *N-m*-CPTHA was prepared in alcohol free chloroform.

2*M* solution of AnalaR grade ammonium thiocyanate was prepared in glass distilled water.

Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by the method of West¹².

Procedure : An aliquot of oxidized solution containing 0.02 to 0.12 mg of vanadium was taken

* To whom correspondence should be made.

in a separatory funnel, then distilled water and hydrochloric acid was added to adjust the acidity between 5.0 to 8.0 *M*. 10 ml of 0.1% reagent solution was added and shaken for 1 minute. 5 ml of 2 *M* aqueous solution of ammonium thiocyanate was added and the mixture was shaken for 20 minutes. The chloroform layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate in a 25 ml beaker. Then the aqueous phase was washed twice with 4 ml of chloroform. The chloroform extracts were transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask and then diluted to the mark with chloroform. The absorbance was measured at 580 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. It was noted that if the thiocyanate was added after separating the chloroform extract then the change in colour takes place after two hours.

Results and Discussion

A red-violet complex with vanadium(V) and *m*-CPTHA is formed in 5 to 8 *M* hydrochloric acid medium which is readily extractable in chloroform and shows the maximum absorbance at wavelength 520 nm having $\epsilon_{\max} 5850 \pm 50 \text{ l.mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. When aqueous thiocyanate solution is added to the chloroform solution of vanadium(V)-*N-m*-CPTHA complex, the wavelength of maximum absorption shifts to longer wavelength and the absorbance increases, with increasing concentration of thiocyanate to more than 0.2 *M* both the wavelength of maximum absorbance and absorbance remains constant (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectra of Vanadium (V)-*N-m*-Chlorophenyl-2-Theo-Hydroxamate in Chloroform-Acidity before adding Thiocyanate-6*M* HCl and Acidity after adding Thiocyanate-3*M* HCl

Vanadium concentration- $1.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}/25 \text{ ml}$ ($82 \mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$)

Thiocyanate concentration — = none,

b — o-o-o = 1×10^{-4} , c — x x x = 2×10^{-4} , d — - - - = 3×10^{-4} ,

e — = 4×10^{-4} , f — -x-x- = 5×10^{-4} , g — -o-o- = 6×10^{-4}

Vanadium is completely extracted into chloroform from 5-8 *M* hydrochloric acid irrespective of the absence or presence of thiocyanate.

The molar absorptivity of the vanadium(V)-*N-m*-CPTHA complex in presence of thiocyanate is found $7000 \pm 50 \text{ l.mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at $\lambda_{\max} 580 \text{ nm}$ giving Sandell's sensitivity $0.00728 \mu\text{g V cm}^{-2}$.

Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 0.8 ppm to 4.8 ppm. The colour system is found stable at least for 24 hrs. The blue coloured complex of vanadium(V) is extractable into chloroform and other organic solvents such as benzene, dichlorobenzene, amylalcohol and solvent ether but chloroform was found to be the most suitable solvent due to the better solubility of the reagent in it and faster separation of aqueous and organic phases.

It was noted that if the thiocyanate was added before the addition of the reagent (*N-m*-CPTHA) during extraction then shift to longer wavelength and change in colour intensity do not take place. No reason for this could be assigned.

The following ions do not interfere even if present in large excess (200 folds) Ca^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Ag^{+} , Be^{+2} , Mg^{+2} , Hg^{+2} , Mn^{+2} , Ba^{+2} , Cd^{+2} , Fe^{+2} , Li^{+} , La^{+3} , Al^{+3} , As^{+3} , Zn^{+2} , Cd^{+2} , Sn^{+2} , Sr^{+2} , UO_2^{+2} , Pb^{+2} , ClO_4^- , phosphate, tartrate, citrate, oxalate.

Ti(IV) interferes: Mo(VI) , W(VI) and Zr(IV) which interfere in the determination of vanadium with other hydroxamic acids including *N-m*-CPTHA do not interfere upto 500 ppm with *N-m*-CPTHA in presence of thiocyanate. The presence of these ions in aqueous phase was tested by reported method¹³. Mo(VI) , W(VI) and Zr(IV) form complexes with SCN^- which are not extractable in chloroform.

Composition of the Blue Vanadium(V)-N-m-CPTHA Thiocyanate Complex: An attempt was made to determine the stoichiometric composition of the complex formed between vanadium(V), *N-m*-CPTHA and thiocyanate. Job's method of continuous variation¹⁴ as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper¹⁵ was employed to determine the empirical ratio of vanadium to *N-m*-CPTHA in presence of excess of thiocyanate. The method shows the molar ratio of vanadium to *N-m*-CPTHA to be 1 : 2. The ratio of thiocyanate complex could not be determined by this method. Other methods such as log-log plot method¹⁶ and mole-ratio method¹⁷ were also employed to determine the mole ratio of vanadium to thiocyanate. However, usual spectrophotometric method failed to give any definite composition because the amount of thiocyanate required is in very large excess (1 : 300) and not exactly stoichiometric. A large number of hydroxamic acids reported earlier¹⁸⁻²⁰, were used for

determination of vanadium in presence of thiocyanate but none of them was found to give the reaction described above. It was found that only those hydroxamic acids which contain the electrophilic substituent such as oxygen or sulphur in c-phenyl ring give the reaction. This may be probably due to greater sensitivity and selectivity expected in the presence of electronegative substituent.

It will thus be seen that the present method is highly selective and sensitive for the determination of vanadium(V) and it can be used for analysis of vanadium(V) in complex materials. The reliability of the method has been listed by analysing B.C.S. standard steels. The data is reproduced below.

Determination of vanadium in steel: Vanadium was determined in British Chemical Standard Steels.

An aliquot of sample solution²¹ taken and vanadium content was determined as reported above. The results of analysis are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN B. C. S. STEELS

B. C. S. Steels	Vanadium found*%	Certified value%	Standard deviation
241/1 High speed steel	1.550	1.570	±.0025
252 Low alloy steel	0.485	0.460	±.0030
64 Alloy steel	1.555	1.570	±.0027

* Average of five analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. G. Tandon, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur for providing facilities and one

of them (K.P.) is thankful to Ravishankar University for the award of fellowship.

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